

Thermo-osmosis of Water and Aqueous Solutions across Clay Membranes

KAUSHIK MAJUMDAR** and SAROJ KUMAR SANYAL*

Department of Agricultural Chemistry and Soil Science, Bidhan Chandra Krishi Viswavidyalaya, Kalyani-741 235

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Thermo-osmosis of water and aqueous solutions of hydrochloric acid, acetic acid and magnesium chloride was studied across bentonite and kaolinite clay membranes in the hydrogen form. A three-part osmotic cell was designed for the purpose and used. The corresponding heat of transport was obtained by fitting the measured steady state concentration, temperature, hydrostatic pressure and osmotic pressure differences across the clay membranes to formulations based on irreversible thermodynamics of such coupled transport processes. The resulting values of heat transport were all positive, and interpreted in terms of the changes in entropy of the clay-sorbed water and aqueous solutions as compared to that in the bulk phases.

THERE have been earlier reports of studies of non-isothermal transport processes in soil¹, even though the qualitative aspects of these studies were left largely unemphasised upon. The latter have since been examined, and the importance of heat of transport in characterising soil-moisture interactions has been highlighted^{2,3}. In the present paper, these concepts are extended to such transport processes in a discontinuous system, namely, thermo-osmosis of water and aqueous electrolytes across clay membranes, such as H-bentonite and H-kaolinite, in which field very little work has been done so far.

Experimental

Non-isothermal osmotic cell : The thermo-osmotic cell with elaborate arrangements for various *in situ* measurements, was designed from a perspex block and stainless steel and fabricated for thermoosmotic studies of water and aqueous solutions across clay membranes. The cell consisted of three sections (Fig. 1), namely, the central perspex part and the upper and lower stainless steel water jackets. The middle cylindrical perspex portion had two small solution chambers (hot and cold) separated from each other by a sandwiched perspex sheet which was provided with a small hole. The clay membrane under study was fixed in this hole with an adhesive. Each half-cell was provided with two face-to-face platinum conductivity electrodes and two side-tubes with standard joints. These side-tubes were used for filling the cell with water or aqueous solutions under examination. The three parts of the thermo-osmotic cell were held together by brass nuts and bolts, screwed through the outer peripheral parts of the perspex block as well as the aligned stainless steel flanges of the water jackets. A heating element, covered by glass

fibres, was wrapped round the upper (hot) stainless steel jacket containing water, the temperature of

Fig. 1. Thermo-osmotic cell.

which was regulated by a thermoregulating arrangement consisting of an electrical contact thermometer inserted into the steel chamber through a rubber cork, as well as a solid state relay unit. The lower (cold) stainless steel chamber was kept cooled by circulating appropriately thermostated water using inlet and outlet tubes fixed to the chamber.

The temperature of each half-cell was periodically monitored by means of a copper-constantan thermocouple junction suitably in contact with each half-cell. The concentration changes

**Present address : Department of Soils and Crops, State University of Rutgers, Lipman Hall, P.O. Box-231, New Brunswick, NJ 08903, U.S.A.

of the aqueous electrolyte were measured periodically in terms of the corresponding changes in conductivity using the *in situ* platinum conductivity electrodes. Two capillary (graduated) tubes were connected through standard joints to each half-cell for recording and hydrostatic flow through the membrane. The whole set-up was mounted vertically, and insulated against ambient temperature fluctuations using glass wool.

Preparation of membrane: A measured quantity (25 g) of refined bentonite and kaolinite (organic matter-free) was treated separately with water and kept for two days to transfer it to reactive stage. After two days, an excess amount of dilute HCl was added to transform the pure clays into H-form. On allowing equilibration for 72 h, both the samples were washed several times to remove the excess acid. After the supernatant reached a pH close to 7.0, the two clay samples were dialysed against double-distilled water to wash out the chloride present. The clay suspensions were then boiled on a water-bath to evaporate excess water, and the dense suspension was then poured slowly into a shallow glass disc, previously rubbed with a piece of linen, soaked with liquid paraffin. The thickness of the membrane varied from 0.20 to 0.26 mm. The membranes thus prepared were cut into suitable sizes (diameter greater than 8 mm) and fired at 500° for 5 h in a muffle furnace. The H-bentonite and H-kaolinite membranes thus prepared were then mounted in the circular groove of the membrane assembly of the cell using Araldite as the adhesive. Once mounted, the membranes were found to be fairly stable for thermoosmotic experiments.

Experimental run: The experiments conducted covered thermoosmosis of water and aqueous HCl across H-bentonite and H-kaolinite membranes, and that of aqueous acetic acid and MgCl₂ across H-bentonite membrane.

Before an actual run, the clay membrane, mounted as described above, was moistened with distilled water for 24 h to remove any entrapped air bubble. Both the half-cells were then filled with water or the aqueous solution under investigation, taking care to exclude air bubbles. The temperature of the upper stainless steel chamber was increased steadily to a desired higher value by the wrapped heating arrangement. The temperature of the bottom half-cell was kept lower by circulating thermostated water into the lower stainless steel jacket with the help of a pump. The temperature of each half-cell was monitored periodically using the copper-constantan thermocouple junctions as described earlier. The thermo-osmotic flow of water through the clay membrane was ascertained by recording the rate of development of hydrostatic pressure head difference between the glass capillary tubes emerging from both the half-cells.

For studying thermo-osmosis of aqueous solutions of electrolytes, the solution concentrations and

their changes were noted from time to time by measuring the conductivity (as a function of time) of the solution in each half-cell. The attainment of steady state was indicated by these concentration differences across the membrane (in addition to the pressure head differences in the glass capillary tubes corrected for unequal thermal expansion in the two half-cells) registering constant values independent of time. The time of attainment of the steady state was in agreement with the requirements of relaxation time of the process⁴. The steady state concentrations of HCl and MgCl₂ were obtained from the corresponding *in situ* conductivity measurements while making due allowance for the temperature effect on such conductivities. These concentrations agreed well with determinations conducted (by conductometric titrations) on suitable aliquots withdrawn at the steady state from both the half-cells. The concentrations of acetic acid solutions at the steady state were ascertained by this latter means of analysis.

The steady state osmotic pressure difference ($\Delta\pi$) as is required to compute the heat of transport (\hat{Q}) by equation (1) was obtained for each solution from the appropriate measured value of Δm . Thus \hat{Q} is given by^{4,5}

$$\hat{Q} = \nu B_1 RT^2 \sigma_1 - T(\bar{V}_0 + \bar{V}_1) \left(\frac{\Delta P - \Delta\pi}{\Delta T} \right)_{st} \quad (1)$$

where, \bar{V}_0 and \bar{V}_1 are the respective partial molar volumes of solvent and solute, T the mean absolute temperature while ΔP , $\Delta\pi$ and ΔT refer to the steady state values of the difference of hydrostatic pressure, osmotic pressure and temperature respectively, across the membrane. ν is the number of ions produced by complete dissociation of one molecule of the electrolyte, while B_1 is a thermodynamic factor, given by,

$$B_1 = \left(1 + \frac{\Delta \ln \gamma_1}{\Delta \ln m_1} \right)_{st}$$

where, γ_1 being the mean ionic activity coefficient of the electrolyte and m_1 its mean molality. σ_1 is the Soret coefficient of the solute⁶ and is obtained as

$$\sigma_1 = - \frac{1}{m_1} \left(\frac{\Delta m_1}{\Delta T} \right)_{st}$$

For transport of water across the membrane, $\sigma_1 = 0$, $\bar{V}_1 = 0$ and $\Delta\pi = 0$; hence equation (1) reduces to

$$\hat{Q}_w = - \bar{V}_0 T \left(\frac{\Delta P}{\Delta T} \right)_{st} \quad (2)$$

Equations (1) and (2) are made use of to obtain the heat of transport of the solutions and water, respectively, studied in the present investigation. The heat of transport, so obtained, is formally defined as the amount of heat absorbed per mole of a diffusing species from the region it leaves, and released in the region it moves into under isothermal conditions⁶ with movement of no other component in a multicomponent system. It is

TABLE 1—HEAT OF TRANSPORT OF WATER ACROSS H-KAOLINITE AND H-BENTONITE CLAY MEMBRANES

Membrane	Mean temp. K	\bar{V}_0 ml mol ⁻¹	$\left(\frac{\Delta P}{\Delta T}\right)_{st}$ $\times 10^7$ dyne cm ⁻² K ⁻¹	\hat{Q}_w J mol ⁻¹
H-kaolinite	313.68	18.09	571.91	0.825 ± 0.014
H-bentonite	327.88	18.09	512.98	0.302 ± 0.024

TABLE 2—THERMO-OSMOTIC PARAMETERS OF AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS (0.1 M) ACROSS H-KAOLINITE AND H-BENTONITE CLAY MEMBRANES

Solution	Membrane	Mean T K	\bar{V}_1 ml mol ⁻¹	B_1	σ_1 $\times 10^8$ K ⁻¹	$\nu BRT^2 \sigma_1$ kJ mol ⁻¹	\hat{Q} kJ mol ⁻¹
HCl	H-kaolinite	316.16	18.20	0.945	1.97	8.09	3.09 ± 1.046
HCl	H-bentonite	313.47	18.20	0.945	3.53	5.45	5.45 ± 0.211
Acetic acid	H-bentonite	316.10	17.03	1.00 ^a	2.45	2.05	2.05 ± 0.173
Magnesium chloride	H-bentonite	313.40	95.19	0.855	10.80	22.50	22.60 ± 0.4766

^aIn absence of relevant activity coefficient data, B_1 for acetic acid (0.1 M) solution was assumed to be unity.

known to be sensitive to the nature of interactions inherent in the system^{2,6}.

Results and Discussion

The results of the various thermo-osmotic experiments are entered in Tables 1 and 2. Each experiment under a given set of external conditions was conducted twice, and the heat of transport values recorded refer to the corresponding mean values.

For thermo-osmosis of water, \hat{Q}_w was computed from the observed $(\Delta P/\Delta T)$ value at the steady state by equation (2). For both the clays used, \hat{Q}_w is positive (Table 1) which signifies an absorption of heat behind the diffusing water, and a liberation ahead in course of migration through the membrane phase^{2,6}. A plausible interpretation may be sought in terms of a gain in entropy of water in contact with the clay matrix as compared to that in the bulk phase as a consequence of partial breakdown of the cooperative long-range hydrogen bonded structure of bulk water in the clay phase because of interspersed foreign particles which encourage build-up of 'localised' patches of ordered structures in sorbed water (resulting from clay-water interactions). That \hat{Q}_w is higher in case of H-kaolinite than for H-bentonite (Table 1) is also in agreement with this picture in view of a stronger orienting influence of bentonite (on water), characterised by a much higher C.E.C. than kaolinite. The latter causes a 'narrowing down' of entropy gain of diffusing water in contact with the clay particles for bentonite, and hence a lower \hat{Q}_w .

The \hat{Q} values for aqueous solutions are also seen to be positive (Table 2), and can be interpreted in the same manner as above. The required B_1 values were calculated by using the activity coefficient data reported in literature⁷.

\hat{Q} for HCl (0.1 M) across H-kaolinite is much lower than that for H-bentonite. This is probably

connected with the unusual transport mechanism of aqueous proton which leaves behind almost entirely the structured hydration shell. The water molecules present in the latter relax (as the centrally located H⁺ ion diffuses away) from their electrostricted state to the normal cooperative network, which is accompanied by an absorption of heat at the membrane surface, immediately behind the diffusing HCl. i.e. a positive \hat{Q} . However, the passage of H⁺ ion through the negatively charged clay membrane phase (hydrated) by the unusual mechanism as above is expected to be somewhat inhibited, unless a sufficiently strong H⁺ ion concentration is built up at the entry point on the membrane surface, ensuing from the stripping away of the corresponding large sphere of hydration hull of these H⁺ ions. The C.E.C. of bentonite being much higher than that of kaolinite, it is no wonder that the above relaxation effect of stripped off water molecules would also be much greater. This would cause a higher \hat{Q} for bentonite than for kaolinite, as observed in the present study (Table 2).

With acetic acid, the degree of dissociation at 0.1 M concentration being only about 1%, the predominant diffusing species being the undissociated acid itself. The corresponding passage through bentonite is, therefore, practically free of any inhibitory effects (exerted by the charged membrane phase) referred to above and the transport mechanism of aqueous acetic acid being quite the usual one, the respective \hat{Q} value is expected to be much lower than that for HCl (0.1 M) across H-bentonite. This indeed is observed experimentally (Table 2).

For aqueous MgCl₂ (0.1 M), the diffusion through H-bentonite membrane is likely to be accompanied by a high degree of ion-exchange between H⁺ and Mg²⁺ occurring in the clay, Mg²⁺ being characterised by a high bonding energy on the clay matrix. This would further inhibit the diffusive transport of Mg²⁺ ions through the clay leading

to a much larger \bar{Q} (than for HCl across H-bentonite), as found here (Table 2).

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